

MODERN METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN HIGHER EDUCATION

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Annotation: The article examines different strategies of teaching foreign languages in higher educational institutions. Specific consideration was paid to the taking after strategies: the coordinate strategy, grammar-translation, audio-visual, audio-lingual, and communicative. It is concluded that the communicative strategy has begun getting to be the most dominant.

Keywords: language, coordinate strategy, grammar-translation, audio-visual method, audio-lingual method, communicative method, practical skills.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются различные стратегии обучения иностранным языкам в высших учебных заведениях. Особое внимание было уделено следующим стратегиям: координационная стратегия, грамматико-переводная, аудиовизуальная, аудиолингвальная и коммуникативная. Делается вывод о том, что коммуникативная стратегия стала становиться доминирующей.

Ключевые слова: язык, координатная стратегия, грамматика-перевод, аудиовизуальный метод, аудиолингвальный метод, коммуникативный метод, практические навыки.

A foreign language today is not just a part of the culture of a particular nation, but it is also the key to success, the future successful career of students. Achieving a high level of proficiency in a foreign language is impossible without fundamental language training in higher education. In most universities in the country, students master at least two foreign languages.

It is important for the teacher to know the latest methods of teaching a foreign language, special teaching techniques and techniques in order to optimally select one or another teaching method in accordance with the level of knowledge, needs, interests of students. After all, teaching methods are not what simple "algorithmized units", their rational and motivated use in foreign language lessons requires a creative approach on the part of the teacher, because "pedagogy is a science and an art at the same time, therefore the approach to the choice of teaching methods should be based on the teacher's creativity. ". The purpose of this article is to review current trends in the development of methods of teaching foreign languages in higher education. What do scientists mean by the concept of "method"? Teaching methods are "orderly ways of teaching and learning activities aimed at the effective development of the obligations of teaching and educational tasks." The teaching method acts as a

"tool of the teacher's activity for the performance of a leading function - teaching."

Currently, there are many methods for studying a foreign language in higher educational institutions. Each of the methods has certain characteristics, some are more popular and in demand, some less. This article will cover the basic techniques for learning English by students. Modern methods of teaching English in higher educational institutions In the modern world, English is very popular, moreover, this language is the language of international communication, it is known all over the world. Today there are a huge variety of methods for teaching English. In addition, new ones are regularly developed, so now each teacher can choose the most suitable working methodology for himself.

At the present stage of development of science, technology, international trade, various types of business communication, knowledge of foreign languages is not only a necessity, but also a need for specialists. There are many traditional methods of teaching foreign languages that are quite effective. However, the modern development of society requires the search and use of more advanced methods and technologies. Knowledge of several languages is becoming the norm. For fast and effective teaching of foreign languages, innovative methods are needed, aimed at the formation of practical skills of a qualified specialist who is able to solve professional problems at the level of foreign language communicative competence.

At present, when teaching a foreign language in higher educational institutions, classical methods are most often used. Namely:

1. Direct method.
2. Grammar-translation teaching method.
3. Audiovisual and audiolingual methods.
4. Communicative method.

In this article we will look at each of the methods given in more detail.

Direct method of teaching a foreign language.

The essence of this technique is that the teacher pays more attention to studying the spoken language directly, which is used in everyday life. The developers of this method considered that the intermediary language, that is, the language in which the teaching is conducted, slows down the learning of a foreign language. Thus, students are artificially introduced into the world of the language they are studying. The entire lesson is conducted in English, the teacher must also give explanations and new topics in English. Only English-language literature is used.

When teaching English through this method, the role of the teacher in the successful assimilation of knowledge by students is key. That is, his speech must be absolutely clear and correct, the pronunciation must be perfect, since the students will constantly repeat exactly after the teacher. An ideal option for a direct teaching method would be to make the teacher a native English speaker [4, p. 147]. The grammar-translation method The grammar-translation method is the main one in the modern education system. This is a classic method that has been used for decades. Its such prevalence is due to the fact that most of the teachers themselves trained using this method. The goal of the grammar-translation method is to learn how to read and translate using grammatical rules. The disadvantages of this method include the fact that not enough attention is paid to the lexical part. The study of vocabulary is reduced to the mechanical memorization of words. Reading and translation is carried out in a strict manner. In addition, the texts offered for reading usually refer to complex fiction, therefore, the student only learns the literary language. Once in the linguistic environment, it will be very difficult for him to understand those around him, even with a good knowledge of the literary language.

Audiovisual and audiolingual methods The essence of both methods is to convey the language through clear structures, memorization takes place with the help of audio and video recordings. The audiovisual teaching method involves illustrating speech with appropriate pictures, that is, students are shown videos, feature films and documentaries in English. In this case, the trainees have two channels of perception, visual and auditory, working simultaneously, as a result of which associations arise in the students' heads, which makes it possible to better memorize the language. The purpose of the methods is to master a living, spoken language [1, p. 411]. Both methods are based on induction - learning goes from rule to example. Considering all of the above, it can be noted that for university students who do not specialize in the study of languages, audiolingual and audiovisual methods are suitable only if they are used in conjunction with other training programs [6, p. 109].

Communicative method

Currently, more and more teachers are turning to the communicative method of learning English. The object of this method is speech itself, that is, such a technique primarily teaches to communicate. The communicative method implies a lot of student activity. The task of the teacher in this case will be to involve everyone in the classroom in the conversation. For better memorization

and use of the language, it is necessary to download all the channels of perception.

The essence of the communicative method is to create real communication situations. When recreating the dialogue, the student has the opportunity to put into practice all the knowledge gained. A very important advantage of the communicative method can be considered that it has a huge variety of exercises: role-playing games, dialogues, simulation of real communication are used here [2, p. 85].

At first, the communicative method was rejected, but now it again occupies a leading position along with the traditional grammar-translation method. Most of the teachers of modern universities prefer these two methods, and they are often used in combination. The direct method in higher education is extremely rare, partly due to the lack of true native speakers among teachers, and partly due to the fact that the level of preparation of students after school is too low. The pure audiovisual and audiolingual methods are not used at all, however, many university and institute teachers from time to time conduct classes based on such methods. This allows you to diversify the general education program and interest students.

Thus, the use of a variety of innovative methods of teaching foreign languages has a number of advantages that help teach students to actively acquire new knowledge, develop their creative and organizational skills, and provide a powerful incentive to learn the language. Innovative technologies make it possible to ideally combine theory with practice, form knowledge of the subject, professional skills and abilities.

From all of the above, it should be concluded that today it is important for a teacher to constantly improve his knowledge of methods of teaching foreign languages, introduce the latest educational concepts into his teaching practice, and keep up with the times.

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